

COMPOSITION OF STUDENTS' INTELLECTUAL COMPETENCES

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Abstract. This article reveals the structure of intellectual competence, motivational, cognitive and metacognitive components of intellectual competence. In these paper, the competency-based approach in education includes the ideas of professional and general, intellectual development, and competencies include traditional knowledge, as well as general education, intellectual, communicative, creative, interrelationships. The forms of interdependence and metasubject embodied are highlighted.

Keywords: metacomponent, cognitive experience, motivational, cognitive, metacognitive component.

Deep fundamental education based on the latest achievements of science mainly increases the recognition and high prestige of Uzbek engineering education in the world. As engineers and scientists create techniques and technologies that define the frontiers of future research in science, the challenge has become more urgent. The analysis of scientific and technical literature shows that the current stage of development of science and technology is characterized by the priority of technology development.

Technological restructuring of production refers to the ability of a specialist to reconstruct the activity system, who feels the need to constantly replenish or update knowledge. In such conditions, the purpose of training an engineer at a

technical higher educational institution is to form the ability to master the methodological skills of activity, the principles, methods and methods of activity along with the traditional acquisition of knowledge and skills.

J. Raven explains competence as a special ability (skills) needed to effectively perform specific actions in a specific subject area (including highly specialized knowledge, special skills, and ways of thinking). The nature of competence is that it can be manifested only in harmony with human interests and values. Being a mature scientist, teacher, engineer, manager means having different levels of competence (observation, performing certain actions, taking initiative, writing business letters, organizing communication with other people, etc.). In fact, we are talking here about intellectual education in the broadest sense of the word, taking into account future professional specialization. According to J. Raven, all students have different abilities in different types of activity ("competency"), and the teacher should identify and support them. English psychologist J. Raven, the founder of the psychological theory of competence, works with the concept of "Competence - a set of abilities and skills". In the composition of competence, equality defines two components: general competence (abilities, motivation, skills) and competence that promotes successful self-realization in society, regardless of professional activity [1].

In our opinion, development and self-development always involve some internal laws, some self-movement, self-transformation of an object, a system, a person's self, the inner world of a certain self. refers to the construction itself. This process is irreversible, as a result of which there are quantitative and qualitative changes in intellectual, personal and activity characteristics. They are connected and interdependent. Personnel training has a special place as the basis of development. Orientation of the development process is carried out by influencing the mental development of the student, managing his cognitive activity, developing it and having targeted influence.

O.S. Grebenyuk describes the types of thinking in the intellectual sphere (creative, cognitive, theoretical, empirical, divergent, convergent, sanogenic, pathogenic, etc.), thinking style (analytical thinking, imaginative thinking, visual-metaphorical thinking), qualities of the mind (intelligence, flexibility, independence, criticality, the ability to act in the mind, etc.), cognitive processes (attention, imagination, memory, perception), mental operations (isolation, comparison, analysis, synthesis, systematization, abstraction, formalization, concretization, interpretation, etc.), cognitive skills (ability to ask questions, identify and formulate a problem, hypothesize, prove it, draw conclusions, apply knowledge), learning skills (plan, set) setting goals, reading and writing at an appropriate pace, taking notes, etc.), extracurricular knowledge and skills, scientific knowledge, skills and competencies, general education and special knowledge are characterized by an integrated system [2].

As noted by R. Wagner, a person with intelligence knows how to overcome a certain task, knows how to plan his time and calculate his strength to complete the task [3].

For example, a group of scientists, G. Seydi and A. Wimby, describe intelligence as a "set of skills". Similar ideas can be observed in A. de Groot's definition of intelligence. He calls it a mental program consisting of a number of heuristics. R. Nickerson defines intelligence as "skills, heuristics, methods, strategies, tactics—these are different words for the same idea—teachable components of intellectual thinking" to teach ways of thinking. B. Russell makes the following conclusion about the formula of intellectual thinking: "It is a process of evaluation or categorization in terms of previously acquired basic knowledge, it includes attitudes, as well as having facts and a number of thinking skills" [3].

L.S. Vygotsky believed that the best indicator of intelligence is not the level of knowledge accumulated up to a certain time, but how people learn new things [4].

American psychologist R. Sternberg is the author of the work "three theories of mind", in which he expressed the opinion that the problem of mind should be solved in the context of a wider problem, that is, how the subject manages himself. This theory is based on the answers to three questions: 1) what is the relationship between the mind and the inner world; 2) what is the mind's attitude to the outside world; 3) how intelligence relates to human experience. Within this theory, intelligence is defined as a form of mental self-management, which includes three interrelated subtheories: component, context, and experience theories. These components include:

1. metacomponents - the processes of organizing intellectual activity, including planning, observing how the solution is revealed, choosing the form of presenting the problem, consciously dividing attention, and organizing opinions;
2. performance components - processes of changing information, processes of forming feedback (linking, adding, comparing, selecting, grouping, coding);
3. components of knowledge acquisition and use (knowledge acquisition) processes, efficiency of application at the right time) [5].

In our opinion, intelligence is the quality of a specific form of organization of individual (mental) experience that provides the ability to effectively perceive, understand and explain what is happening. The idea of mental experience as a special mental reality that determines the characteristics of human intellectual activity (the carrier of mental characteristics) was formed in foreign and domestic research. Individual mental experience is considered a system of mental mechanisms that predetermine the type of cognitive attitude. Depending on the specific features of the composition and structure of these forms of experience, we can distinguish convergent abilities (solving normative problems in regulated situations), divergent abilities (creating new ideas based on non-standard methods of activity, acquiring

new knowledge and skills ability), we can observe and measure the learning of cognitive styles (the ability to have individual specific forms of cognitive reflection).

We believe that the intellectual development of students includes not only the development of cognitive mechanisms of information processing, but also the formation of metacognitive mechanisms of intellectual self-control.

Analyzing the works of R. Glazer, V. Schneider, J. Raven, M.A. Kholodnaya, the following can be noted: intellectual competence is the main one, its formation creates the basis for the development of students in all educational areas without exception [6].

Intellectual competence includes all components of the general educational content of education: general educational skills, meta-knowledge and subjective methods of activity. As a result, students have information skills, preparation for self-education, independent search, selection and use of information, the ability to use new technologies of interaction with information, striving to improve the methods of self-knowledge. , a desire to engage in scientific research is formed [7].

Thus, intellectual competence is a personal system of working with information; the ability to acquire and create a new system of knowledge as a result of shifting the semantic context of activity from functional to transformative; determines readiness to revise outdated thinking stereotypes and forms of perception that hinder mobility in professional activity. Intellectual competence determines such features as openness and flexibility in the perception of new things, variability and diversity of subjective ways of understanding the same phenomenon, awareness of different mental "views" of current events [8-12].

M.A. Kholodnaya defines intellectual competence as a special type of knowledge organization that provides the ability to make effective decisions on a specific topic of activity (including extreme conditions) [6]. The requirements for the organization of knowledge are not limited by the size, strength, importance of mastering. They are different types of knowledge, articulation (the main elements

are clearly defined and in a certain relationship with each other), flexibility (in situations where knowledge and the relationships between them can change rapidly under the influence of various factors), a specific situation (knowledge effectiveness), transferring knowledge to a new state, wide application of knowledge, categorical (ideas related to general principles, approaches, reflexivity of knowledge play a decisive role. Intellectual competence is the ability to pose problems of different levels of complexity and The internal quality that provides the possibility of effective solution means the desire to mobilize one's intellectual abilities and personal qualities to solve professional problems based on the activation of personal experience. Thus, competence is the result of self-organization and reflection of individual mental experience. Competence can be manifested only in a coherent unity with the abilities and skills of a person [13-15].

Intellectual activity planning skills include the following: the ability to choose a reasonable and optimal way to achieve the set goals; the possibility of determining the criteria for evaluating the result, drawing up a plan (action program); determine the sequence and duration of independent activity; the ability to hold several alternatives in mind at the same time to solve problems; ability to assess and control, tools and methods of assessment and control, to understand the ownership criteria, control and assessment activities, to understand algorithms, to self-evaluate and selfmonitor their activities, to assess their ability activity results; ability to compare predicted and actually obtained results; skills based on self-monitoring and self-assessment include selfeducation and self-development, development of new tasks.

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